

Book of Abstracts

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evaluated visually by two experienced observers scoring under- and over-segmentation rate (scale 0-3), using intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) to assess inter-observer agreement.

Results or Findings: The mean Dice score for SAT and VAT was 0.95 and 0.85, and VS for SAT and VAT was 0.98 and 0.93. The mean under- and over-segmentation rates of the two observers and the agreement between them were 2.92 (ICC 0.931) and 2.99 (ICC 0.922) for SAT, and 2.99 (ICC 0.956) and 2.95 (ICC 0.778) for VAT respectively, indicating excellent segmentation quality across individuals. The correlation coefficients of VAT with SAT, fat mass and BMI were 0.851, 0.801 and 0.698, respectively.

Conclusion: We retrained and evaluated a deep-learning method to accurately and automatically extract abdominal SAT and VAT volumes from whole-body MRIs of adolescents. These volumes will be used to study determinants of body composition in the Generation R Study.

Limitations: In longitudinal studies of children and adolescents such as Generation R, the CDFNet model must be retrained and validated for each follow-up time point representing different ages.

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RPS 1305-5

MRI-based artificial intelligence (AI) for abdominal adipose tissue segmentation: a meta-analysis

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Purpose: Manual segmentation of subcutaneous and visceral fat tissue on MRI to calculate body composition parameters is difficult. AI allows for a chance to automate this operation. Through systematic review and meta-analysis, we assessed the available AI segmentation solutions based on MRI and their role in body composition analysis.

Methods or Background: We systematically searched PubMed (MEDLINE), Embase and Scopus. We extracted the studies about using MRI-based AI models for subcutaneous (SAT) and visceral adipose tissue (VAT) segmentation, published from January 1, 2011, to October 20, 2022. Studies that used CT and other imaging modalities were excluded. The reported dice similarity coefficient (DSC) of AI models was used for meta-analysis.

Results or Findings: A total of 213 studies were identified. Among them, 26 could be included in the systematic review, of which eight were included in the meta-analysis. Machine-learning models for SAT and VAT segmentation showed a combined DSC of 0.971 (95 %CI 0.962–0.980) and 0.960 (95 %CI 0.951–0.969), respectively. Considerable heterogeneity of included studies was observed.

Conclusion: MRI-based AI models are promising tools for automated subcutaneous and visceral adipose tissue segmentation. More definitive guidelines are necessary before their integration into the routine clinical workflow.

Limitations: Caution should be applied when interpreting results, for they could be skewed by significant heterogeneity between the studies. Also, segmentations were extracted from non-identical abdominal levels; therefore, the models would perform differently and gain different results across these levels. The review was focused solely on MRI-based models, ignoring other imaging modalities.

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RPS 1305-6

Abdominal adipose tissue segmentation and fat percentage calculation by using dual-neural network model

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Purpose: This study designs a convolutional neural network-based dual-model system for fully automatically segmenting abdominal adipose tissue regions on computed tomography (CT) images. This system aims to assist radiologists to

quickly and accurately determine the obesity status of patients by automatically segmenting abdominal adipose tissue and calculating its proportion.

Methods or Background: In current clinical practice, an expert quantifies the fat tissue manually, which is time-consuming. Thus, designing a computer-aided method is essential. We prepared eight patients (2198 2D CT images) for model training; an expert radiologist finished delineating adipose tissue areas in the image. All images were resized, intensity values were normalised, and multiple quantitative metrics were calculated to evaluate the segmentation performance. We trained two models for different segmentation tasks, one is a three-class model that completes the segmentation of subcutaneous adipose tissue (SAT) and visceral adipose tissue (VAT), and the other is a simpler binary classification for segmenting the abdominal region. Accurately finding these three ROIs can calculate values closer to the actual fat percentage.

Results or Findings: Splitting SAT and VAT with mean- $iu=0.972$, dice= 0.980 , acc= 0.986 ; predicting the abdominal region with mean- $iu=0.982$, dice= 0.983 , acc= 0.997 . We calculated the fat percentage of one of the patients; the fat percentage calculated using the annotated image is 49.90%, and using the model-predicted image calculation result is 50.63%. The results prove that the effect of model segmentation is reliable.

Conclusion: We successfully propose a CNN-based dual-model automatic segmentation method with high accuracy and stable performance. According to this method, we can further design and apply it to the clinical diagnosis of the fat status of the patient's body.

Limitations: Our model needs more clinical data to train to improve its robustness, and labelling patient data is a considerable workload. In future research, a method may be proposed to overcome this problem.

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Concordance between artificial intelligence (AI) computed tomography-based and bioimpedance-based analysis of body composition in a prospective study

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Purpose: Body composition as an important indicator of patients' frailty is increasingly recognised. The aim of this prospective trial is to compare body composition parameters obtained from the established bio impedance analysis (BIA) and computed tomography (CT) using an AI-based segmentation method.

Methods or Background: We prospectively included 210 randomly selected patients who underwent contrast-enhanced CT imaging of the abdomen. Before the CT scan, all patients underwent BIA. For CT body composition analysis, an AI-based single-slice segmentation tool was used at the level of L3 (automated detection and segmentation). The BIA-based parameters body fat mass (BFM) and skeletal muscle mass (SMM), and the CT-parameters subcutaneous and visceral adipose tissue area (SATA and VATA) and skeletal muscle area (SMA) were obtained. Body fat percentage (BFP) and skeletal muscle index (SMI) were calculated by normalising the corresponding BIA and CT parameters to weight (BFP) or height (SMI). Parameters representing muscle or fat tissue were gender-specifically evaluated.

Results or Findings: Parameters representing fat and muscle tissue, BIA-based BFM and CT-based SATA+VATA, as well as BIA-based SMM and CT-based SMA, showed a strong correlation in female (fat: $r=0.95$; muscle: $r=0.72$) and male (fat: $r=0.91$; muscle: $r=0.71$) patients ($p<0.001$). Regression analysis was statistically significant and showed that BFP-CT and LSMI-CT could statistically significantly predict BFP-BIA and SMI-BIA for female (BFP: $b1=5.29$; CI95 [4.62-5.95]; SMI: $b1=0.11$; CI95 [0.09-0.13]) and male (BFP: $b1=4.47$; CI95 [3.97-4.97]; SMI: $b1=0.09$; CI95 [0.08-0.11]) patients ($p<0.001$).

Conclusion: AI-based CT body composition parameters strongly correlate with BIA and allow quantification of body fat percentage and skeletal muscle index comparable to the existing gold standard. Thus, an additional BIA appears unnecessary in patients who received an abdominal CT scan as part of their diagnostics.

Limitations: The study's main limitation is its small patient cohort with various diseases.

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